

Novel strategy for toughening robocast bioceramic scaffolds using polymeric cores

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Abstract

A novel method for the fabrication of hybrid polymer/ceramic porous scaffolds with core/shell struts is developed. Robocasting with coaxial needles is used to deposit beta-tricalcium phosphate scaffolds with hollow rods, which are subsequently filled with a polycaprolactone melt by suction. The polymeric core provides outstanding improvement of the toughness of the structure in bending, with strain energy density increasing nearly two orders of magnitude and continuous polymeric fibres holding the structure together even after large deflections. Moreover, flexural strength is not significantly reduced compared to dense-strut structures; and the macroporosity of the scaffold and osteoconductivity of bioceramic surfaces are preserved.

Keywords: Composite scaffolds; ceramic; polymer; mechanical properties; robocasting

1 Biodegradable ceramic scaffolds are an attractive solution to regenerate damaged bone tissue
2 due to their ability to guide, or even to induce the activation of, the cellular mechanisms
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4 involved in natural bone remodelling [1]. Such bioactive materials overcome the typical
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6 drawbacks associated to natural tissue grafts or bioinert implants [2]. They provide structural
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8 support and promote bone growth into their interconnected porous matrix while avoiding
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10 secondary surgical sites, immunogenic response or disease transmission risks. Among the
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12 bioceramic materials eligible for scaffold applications are calcium phosphates [3,4], calcium
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14 sulphate [5,6], bioglasses [7,8] and glass-ceramics [9,10]. Despite their adequate biological
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16 performance, all these materials are intrinsically very brittle, and their strength is typically low,
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18 especially when they are fabricated as highly porous scaffolds to ensure a proper
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20 interconnectivity for vascularization.
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26 The development of additive manufacturing (AM) techniques such as robocasting has
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28 contributed to a greater control over scaffolds geometrical features, including pore
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30 architecture (size, shape, distribution...). This has enabled a reduction in the total porosity
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32 needed to achieve the required pore interconnectivity and, thus, improved scaffolds' load
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34 bearing capacity [11,12]. Nonetheless, strength and, especially toughness of bare bioceramic
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36 robocast scaffolds are still far from matching the mechanical performance of natural bone (Fig.
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38 1). However, significant improvements are achieved on both properties by combining the
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40 inorganic scaffold with a biodegradable polymeric phase[13–17], either by full impregnation of
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42 the structure or by coating its struts. Strength and toughness are, thus, enhanced by
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44 mechanisms of defect healing and crack bridging [18,19]. Furthermore, when the impregnated
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46 polymer occupying the macropores is stiff enough, an additional increase of strength and,
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48 hence, toughness is achieved through stress-shielding: stresses in the ceramic matrix are
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50 diminished as the polymer supports some of the load. The crack bridging mechanism is also
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52 greatly enhanced in fully impregnated structures since the polymeric fibres occupying the
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54 macropores greatly hinder crack propagation. They can, indeed, hold the structure together
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1 long after the ceramic skeleton fails, even at large deformations. This drastically enhances the
2 fracture energy of the hybrid material, which can even surpass that of cortical bone in
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4 compression for some cases (Fig 1a) [8]. Performances are a little bit poorer in bending (Fig.
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6 1b), but fully impregnated structures come substantially closer to natural bone values even
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8 under this most deleterious loading mode.[20–26]
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12 Nevertheless, full impregnation of ceramic scaffolds with polymers (Fig 2a) sacrifices scaffold
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14 macroporosity and prevents, at least initially, colonization of the structure by new tissue.

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17 Polymeric coatings (Fig. 2b) preserve the predesigned macroporosity but still limit the
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19 biological performance of the scaffolds by insulating the bioactive ceramic surface from the
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21 physiological medium. The polymeric barrier delays the release of ions (i.e. Ca^{2+} , PO_4^{3-}) that are
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23 crucial for osteoconduction and osteoinduction [27]. Moreover, degradation mechanisms can
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25 also be hampered, thus reducing resorption rates [28]. Accordingly, hereby we propose a novel
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27 strategy to keep the bioceramic surface exposed to physiological medium by moving the tough
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29 polymeric phase to the interior of the robocast scaffold struts, as depicted in Fig. 2c. This
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31 core/shell architecture would guarantee: i) an open and interconnected macroporosity to
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33 ensure cell proliferation; ii) the presence of ions on the surface to preserve osteoconduction
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35 and improve graft/tissue interfacial bonding, and iii) the presence of continuous polymeric
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37 fibres capable of hampering crack propagation and produce the desired toughening.
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44 In this work, polymer/ceramic hybrid scaffolds with core/shell rod sections are fabricated in a
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46 two-step process: first, ceramic scaffolds with hollow rods are produced by robocasting using
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48 coaxial extrusion (Fig. 2d), and then the rod cores are impregnated with a biodegradable
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50 polymer melt by suction (Fig. 2e). In more detail, beta-tricalcium phosphate (TCP) hollow
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52 scaffolds were fabricated from a concentrated (35 vol.%) colloidal suspension prepared as
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54 described elsewhere [29]. The TCP ink was co-extruded with a fugitive graphite-based ink [30]
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56 through a coaxial nozzle (Linari Engineering S.R.L., Pisa, Italy) with outer internal diameter of
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1.37 mm, and inner external diameter of 0.83 mm. The sacrificial graphite core prevented the collapse of the TCP tubes during the layerwise assembly of the 3D lattice by the robotic deposition device (Aerotech A3200, 3D Inks LLC, Stillwater, OK, USA), which was made within an oil bath. Rods in adjacent layers were oriented orthogonally, and each layer had two end tails to facilitate polymer impregnation. After printing, samples were dried for 5 h and then heat-treated, first at 800 °C for 2 h to burn the graphite, and then sintered at 1200 °C for 1h, all this in air atmosphere. Some of the resulting hollow scaffolds were subsequently impregnated with polycaprolactone (PCL). This was made by immersing one of the end tails in a bath of PCL melt (CAPA 6500, Perstorp Holding AB, $M_w = 50\ 000$) at 220 °C for 6 h, while applying vacuum on the opposite end tail to create suction (Fig. 2e). After this time, PCL polymer filled the core of the scaffold struts and hybrid (PCL/TCP) scaffolds were obtained. For comparative purposes scaffolds with fully dense TCP rods were also printed using a conventional tip with similar internal diameter of 1.36 mm (Nordson EFD).

The morphology and the internal dimensions of the fabricated scaffolds were analysed using scanning electron microscopy (SEM, S-3600N, Hitachi Ltd., Tokyo, Japan) on metallized samples.

Representative SEM micrographs of as-cut transversal sections of hollow, hybrid and dense scaffolds are shown in Fig. 3 at different magnifications. Scaffold's final dimensions were: external strut diameter $d_e = 1.08 \pm 0.03$ mm, internal diameter $d_i = 0.50 \pm 0.02$ mm, centre-to-centre spacing between struts $s = 2.00 \pm 0.08$ mm, and layer height $h = 0.77 \pm 0.03$ mm. Hollow scaffolds (Figs. 3a-c) exhibited straight tubes with round channels, indicating excellent shape retention after extrusion, drying and sintering. Some slight flattening is observable, nonetheless, close to the contact between layers, because of the required layer overlap. The good channel morphology facilitates polymer impregnation, and the hybrid scaffolds (Figs. 3d-f) show a complete occupation of the internal channel volume by PCL. To the best of the authors' knowledge, this is the first successful attempt to produce a 3D structure with hybrid

1 polymer/ceramic core/shell struts—there are a couple of reports on scaffolds with coaxial
2 polymer/polymer struts [31,32]—with non-porous fully-occupied cores. This is a critical feature
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4 to maximize the toughening achieved by impregnation of the scaffolds, since the greater the
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6 amount of polymer inside the channel is, the higher the energy it can absorb during fracture by
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8 crack bridging. Furthermore, as can be seen at the higher magnifications, the polymer
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10 penetrates also to some extent into the micropores of the ceramic shell. This is evidenced by
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12 the polymer fibrils at the ceramic/polymer interface that can be seen at high magnification
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14 (Fig. 3f), which were produced by shear during cutting of these specimens. This also plays a
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16 crucial role on toughening the material, since a greater amount of energy is required to
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18 separate both phases and these polymeric fibrils can also contribute to crack bridging. On the
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20 other hand, the external surfaces of the ceramic shells in hybrid scaffolds (Fig. 2d-e) have a
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22 similar appearance to those of hollow (Fig. 2a-b) and dense (Fig. 2g-h), indicating that polymer
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24 couldn't fully permeate the struts shells, and the external surfaces remained free of polymer.
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26 This suggests that the proposed fabrication strategy should not affect the biological
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28 performance (i.e. osteoconductivity) of the bioceramic, since the presence of PCL exclusively in
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30 the strut cores should not inhibit ion release from TCP.
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38 On the contrary, the effect in terms of mechanical performance is expected to be quite
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40 significant. To evaluate this effect, parallelepiped specimens with dimensions of around
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42 $5 \times 5 \times 5$ and $5 \times 5 \times 27$ mm were cut from each type of scaffolds for uniaxial compressive and
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44 3-point bending tests, respectively. Tests were carried out on a universal testing machine (AG-
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46 IS 10kN, Shimadzu Corp., Kyoto, Japan) at a constant crosshead speed of 0.6 mm/min for
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48 compression tests and 6 mm/min for bending. The load was applied perpendicular to the
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50 printing plane in both cases, as depicted in the schematic insets of Fig. 4. Stress-strain and load
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52 vs. displacement curves were registered, respectively during the tests. Strength values were
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54 estimated from the maxima in those curves and toughness (strain energy density) from the
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56 area under the curves.
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Representative stress-strain curves obtained in compression and load-displacement curves from 3-point bending tests on the fabricated scaffolds are shown in Fig. 4a and b, respectively. A linear elastic behaviour followed by a load drop associated to a catastrophic fracture is observed for both hollow and dense scaffolds. This typical brittle behaviour is especially clear under bending stresses. On the contrary, the curves corresponding to the hybrid scaffolds, while initially exhibiting the same trend, show a more progressive decline after the ceramic skeleton fails and retain a significant load bearing capacity even after relatively high strains/deflections. This residual load bearing capacity, which is especially remarkable in bending, is provided by the polymeric cores.

The results of strength and toughness estimated from these curves are summarized in Figures 4c and 4d, respectively. As indicated, compressive data is shown on the left and bending results on the right half of each figure. Results are compared to natural bone properties given in the literature [24–26]. There is a significant reduction in compressive strength of the robocast scaffolds when the dense rods are substituted by hollow struts. However, this reduction is clearly mitigated after polymer impregnation, with the strength improving by more than 100 % in hybrid scaffolds. On the other hand, there are no substantial strength differences between the three types of scaffolds in bending. That is, unlike in compression, the load bearing capacity of the scaffolds in bending is not jeopardized by the substitution of TCP by PCL or even by air (i.e. in hollow scaffolds) in the cores of the scaffold struts. The explanation for this is to be found on the location of the maximum stresses and thus the initiation of fracture in each case. In compression, applied load is supported by columns of materials along the loading direction and any substitution of a stiff material by a weaker alternative results in a reduction of mechanical performance. In particular, when loading is applied perpendicularly to the printing plane, as done in this study, the ceramic tubes in hollow scaffolds suffer diametral compression and maximum stresses move from the external surface of the rods close to the contacts with adjacent layers [33] to the internal

1 channel surfaces close to those same contacts. This change in the damage mode explains also
2 why infiltration with PCL improves compressive strength so much, since the polymer can
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4 impregnate existing flaws in those internal channel surfaces and produce strengthening by
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6 defect healing [16,18,34,35]. On the contrary, in 3-point bending the maximum stresses are
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8 located at the external surface of the struts opposite the central loading support and do not
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10 depend on the modulus of the bending specimen. This leads to a negligible effect of the core
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12 material on the flexural strength of the scaffolds. Also, since crack propagation starts at the
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14 external surface of the shell, where no polymer is present (Fig. 3), no defect healing could
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16 occur, and hollow and hybrid scaffolds exhibited the same values. Therefore, the proposed
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18 core/shell architecture does not jeopardize the strength —the specific strength actually
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20 increases, in fact, since density decreases — of the scaffolds in bending, where conventional
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22 structures are more lacking in terms of mechanical performance compared to natural bone
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24 (Figs. 1 and 4c). Even though the fabricated scaffolds were not geometrically optimized, and
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26 TCP is not the best of bioceramics in terms of strength, the measured flexural strength values
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28 for the three scaffolds analysed were close to cancellous bone performance.
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36 Furthermore, in terms of toughness (Fig. 4d) — evaluated as strain energy density—, the
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38 proposed architecture produced a very significant advantage. There were only relatively minor
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40 differences in the values measured in hollow scaffolds compared to dense ones in
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42 compression, which vanished after polymer impregnation. However, most importantly, in
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44 bending core/shell hybrid scaffolds exhibited more than one order of magnitude better
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46 performance than hollow and dense scaffolds, which showed similar values in this loading
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48 configuration. This is provided by PCL fibres that bridge the crack as it propagates—as shown
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50 in the *in situ* image included as inset in Fig. 4d—holding the structure together even at large
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52 strains and with a residual load-bearing capacity close to the maximum of the load
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54 displacement curve (Fig. 4b). The outstanding toughening achieved is a very promising result
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56 considering that this study is just a first attempt to evaluate the influence of polymeric cores,
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1 using randomly selected geometrical (shell thickness, rods separation, layers overlap...) and
2 material parameters. Optimization of the core/shell architecture design and materials should
3 yield additional improvements over the already substantial 32-fold increase of toughness
4 achieved here; and could achieve scaffold performances closer to or even surpassing those of
5 natural bone. The impressive toughening enhancement reported in this work becomes even
6 more remarkable when compared to previous studies. Although dimensional differences in
7 the samples and the testing configuration used in each case makes a direct comparison of the
8 values unreliable, it is worth noting that the toughening reported here in bending for the
9 hybrid scaffolds is comparable to those reported in previous works (Fig. 1b), somewhere in
10 between those obtained by polymeric coatings and full impregnation of the robocast scaffolds.
11 This is impressive considering that, unlike in these previous reports, in the current hybrid
12 structures there is no contribution from defect healing to this toughening—note that any
13 strengthening of the structure produces also an increase in the area under the curves, i.e. and
14 increase in toughness. Also, unlike in those cases, this excellent performance is achieved
15 without sacrificing either the interconnected macroporosity required for tissue ingrowth and
16 vascularization nor the exposition of bioceramic surfaces to the biological medium, thus
17 preserving in principle the osteoconductivity and biological performance of the bioceramic
18 scaffold. Although, of course, this extreme would have to be corroborated in subsequent
19 biological *in vitro* and *in vivo* tests. Other aspects to be addressed in future work would be the
20 effect of strut dimensions on the mechanical performance. In this sense, it is worth mentioning
21 that while bigger structures would pose no problem, fabricating scaffolds with smaller features
22 could be challenging due to the limitations imposed by the use of coaxial needles or difficulties
23 in the infiltration process.

24 In conclusion, this work can be considered as a successful proof of concept of a novel route for
25 the fabrication of scaffolds with mechanical performance closer to natural bone's than existing
26 alternatives in bone tissue engineering. It has been possible to fabricate robocast scaffolds

1 with dense polymer/ceramic core/shell struts which have demonstrated to have significantly
2 improved toughness, especially under bending stresses. This toughening effect comes without
3 jeopardizing the flexural strength of the scaffolds. Also, although the compressive strength
4 might be reduced in hybrid scaffolds compared to fully-dense bioceramic struts, the reduction
5 is not dramatic, especially in specific terms. Moreover, unlike more traditional toughening
6 methods based also on polymer impregnation, the proposed strategy provides enhanced
7 toughness without, in principle, affecting the bioactivity of the scaffold surfaces nor the
8 interconnected porosity required for bone tissue regeneration.

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Figure Captions

Figure 1. Comparative plots of strain energy density as a function of strength in (a) compression and (b) bending for bare, coated, and fully-impregnated bioceramic robocast scaffolds from previous works [8,19–23]. Coloured rectangular areas represent natural bone properties [24–26].

Figure 2. Schematic illustrations of hybrid polymer-ceramic robocast scaffolds: (a) fully-impregnated, (b) coated and (c) core-shell structure. Core-shell hybrid scaffolds are fabricated in this work by co-extrusion, depicted in isometric and section view in (d), followed by PCL-impregnation of the resulting sintered tubular scaffold by suction (e).

Figure 3. SEM micrographs at different magnifications of representative cross-sections of the scaffolds fabricated in this work with (a-c) hollow, (d-f) hybrid and (g-i) dense struts.

Figure 4. Top: representative (a) uniaxial compression nominal stress–strain curves and (b) bending load-displacement curves obtained for the different scaffolds fabricated, as indicated.

Bottom: bar diagrams of average (c) strength and (d) strain energy density measured on all structures both in compression and bending. Natural bone values [24–26] are included as yellow bands for comparison.

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